

THE CURRENT STATE OF VETERINARY SERVICE FOR POULTRY FARMING IN UZBEKISTAN AND THE APPLICATION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN IT

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In Uzbekistan, information and computer technologies are practically not used by the veterinary service of livestock enterprises. Scientific developments are extremely few. Previously developed information platforms for improving veterinary care, planning preventive anti-epizootic measures, using computers in veterinary practice, introducing an electronic system for maintaining veterinary records and generating veterinary reporting documents, and using electronic databases by veterinary specialists are outdated and do not meet modern requirements in this area. At the same time, such areas of veterinary services as the development of a plan for veterinary and sanitary measures, the maintenance of veterinary registers in order to form veterinary reporting documents, and the economic analysis of veterinary measures require software. Due to the use of modern information technologies, it is possible to significantly reduce the time spent on certain types of veterinary work, especially organizational and managerial, and, most importantly, to minimize or eliminate the possibility of errors made in the implementation of labor activities, which is currently a necessary condition for the effective organization of veterinary poultry services.

Currently, a spreadsheet is widely used in document management, since its functions are multifaceted, it can be used to create a wide variety of action algorithms and simplify labor actions during repeated, repetitive work with the same type of data, and MS Excel is a tool for performing the required operations. Research scientists have found that in veterinary care it is important to form an algorithm of actions at a certain stage of veterinary care in such a way that you can manage the database and get an accurate result. In this case, the algorithm can be implemented not only in the MS Excel processor, but also in MS Access. After the development of an algorithm that excludes erroneous user actions when performing job functions, it is possible to perform programming. This is achieved using the Visual Basic for Applications (VBA) language, a programming language, as well as an integrated development environment for software from Microsoft Corporation. Visual Basic for Applications represents a

groundbreaking development in programming languages, perhaps the most significant since the first IDE was released. VBA combines almost unlimited possibilities with ease of learning and use. The most important advantage of VBA is that this language is the same for all Microsoft office applications and therefore allows you to link them together. From a program written in Excel, you can access Word for Windows objects as well as Microsoft Project.

The digitalization of modern society has an impact on the characteristics of the organization of labor, similar to the action of catalysts that can change the organizational and technical environment for the implementation of a set of veterinary and sanitary measures. Nevertheless, it can be assumed that the problem of implementing software in the veterinary services of agro-industrial enterprises is due to the lack of a single clear algorithm of actions in the implementation of certain veterinary activities: even when the necessary production indicators are achieved in the field of meeting veterinary and sanitary requirements, methods for obtaining results for each poultry farm businesses are different. And the need for software can be considered realized if, at certain stages of veterinary care (planning, economic analysis, document flow), it will be possible to enter the initial data and see the finished result.

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